

The Application of Deep Learning Imputation and Other Advanced Methods for Handling Missing Values in Network Intrusion Detection

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In intelligent information systems data play a critical role. The issue of missing data is one of the commonplace problems occurring in data collected in the real world. The problem stems directly from the very nature of data collection. In this paper, the notion of handling missing values in a real-world application of computational intelligence is considered. Two experimental campaigns were conducted, evaluating different approaches to the missing values imputation on Random Forest-based classifiers, trained using modern cybersecurity benchmarks datasets: CICIDS2017 and IoT-23. In result of the experiments it transpired that the chosen algorithm for data imputation has a severe impact on the results of the classifier used for network intrusion detection. It also comes to light that one of the most popular approaches to handling missing data — complete case analysis — should never be used in cybersecurity.

Keywords: Data science; missing data; incomplete data; cybersecurity; data imputation.

1. Introduction

In machine learning and its applications, data preparation is crucial and often can take up a significant portion of effort in the data engineering endeavor. A slight data quality adjustment can potentially contribute to a compelling boost in the performance of ML.¹

One of the most prevailing flaws of the data coming from the real world is the issue of missing data. The notion of properly handling missing data remains a relevant issue for most of the Machine Learning (ML) applications.² The problem stems directly from the very nature of data collection and assumes different forms.

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Each form — or pattern — of missingness results with some ramifications for the ML algorithms used down the road.³ Properly handling missing data is of utmost importance and has to be put under particular scrutiny to make sure ML methods are going to construct accurate reasoning.⁴ Data that are missing may hold valuable information on the dataset.⁵ Moreover, many ML methods do not support data with values missing.⁶

There are different approaches to handle the problem; some of them are prevalent in contemporary applications, despite their flaws. The research community also offers more robust methods, such as multiple imputations, applicable to many situations.³ This process starts with an attentive inspection of the data.² The premise of handling missing data is that the missing features can be inferred from the remainder of the dataset. In fact, in the example described in Ref. 7, some imputations are fairly straightforward. In the context of ‘nonresponse’ to a survey, where the missing response is part of several waves of measurements, they can be inferred from the measurements before and after the missing values with exceptional accuracy through interpolation.⁷ Similarly, if the respondent stopped providing measurements after a certain measurement, a situation referred to as ‘attrition’, the missing data can be approximated via extrapolation.⁷ When measurements are missing in a dataset, the processes necessary for pattern classification increase in complexity.⁸ In intrusion detection, there are sometimes values missing in the NetFlow reports, which in turn disable the ability to calculate certain features. Imputation is one of the ways to handle this predicament.

In this work, the problem of handling missing values in network intrusion detection has been addressed. Specifically, this work searches for the answers to the following research questions:

- RQ1: What is the impact of missing data handling procedures on cybersecurity applications?*
- RQ2: Can the choice of the imputation method influence the effectiveness of ML-based NIDS?*
- RQ3: Which imputation methods are best suited for handling missing data in cybersecurity applications?*

The text is structured as follows: Section 2 opens with an introduction to the problem of data quality and missing data, the missingness mechanisms are introduced and discussed. This is followed by introducing visual analytics for handling missing data, discussing the related work in this subject, in Sec. 3. Then, the used visual analytics for the selected case are shown in the same section. The work continues with an inventory of approaches to dealing with missing data in Sec. 4, along with the most applicable algorithms in the context of network intrusion detection. The pros and cons of the methods are disclosed. Then, the details of the experiments are given and the results obtained are communicated in Sec. 5. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

This paper is an extended version of Ref. 9, first presented during the “13th Asian Conference on Intelligent Information and Database Systems”. Specifically, it expands the original work in the following aspects:

- It outlines the state-of-the-art Deep Learning (DL) approaches to the missing data imputation task,
- It compares the impact of a deep learning imputation and the commonly used imputation methods on the results of a Balanced Random Forest Classifier¹⁰ model trained on a subset of IoT-23 dataset,¹¹ simulating heavily depleted data,
- Provides further insights and conclusions on the subject of missing and incomplete data handling in cybersecurity applications.

2. Related Works

In Ref. 12, the usage of deep learning imputation in the form of Autoencoders (AE) for tabular data is presented. The survey collects 26 articles between 2014 and 2020 to provide a perspective on Autoencoders and how well they perform compared to other approaches. AEs learn a representation of the data by trying to reproduce input in the output layer.¹² This characteristic makes it possible for the Autoencoders to learn from missing data and thus suitable for the imputation task. Particularly the Denoising Autoencoders (DAE)¹³ are designed for the recovery of noisy data i.e. corrupted or missing.¹² During the training, DAEs apply some form of stochastic corruption, such as Gaussian noise, to the input.

Moreover, the authors of Ref. 12 also highlight another variant that has lately become popular — the Variational Autoencoder (VAE). Instead of learning a latent representation of the data, this variant determines a set of distribution parameters describing it. The VAE can then sample those parameters to generate new data instances possessing identical characteristics.¹⁴ Adversarial Autoencoders, which also use variational inference but extend it with the concept of adversarial loss,¹⁵ are also touched upon.

According to the survey,¹² the AEs often use a pre-imputation step with one of the methods described earlier. This step is performed because most popular loss functions will not handle missing data directly.

The Surveyed algorithms in Ref. 12 were usually applied for data with substantial missing rates, reaching 90% in some cases. Nevertheless, the tested approaches, using either Denoising or Variational autoencoders, achieved better results than other methods in most scenarios. To be precise, in nearly 85% of all investigated cases, Autoencoders were better than the competition. This fact is assigned to the ability of Artificial Neural Networks to model relations with greater complexity than the traditional methods. However, these are just some of the benefits of AEs in this context. The authors of Ref. 12 also accentuate the native support for multivariate scenarios and quick execution times after obtaining the trained model.

There are some drawbacks of using Autoencoders. First, they usually demand extensive pre-processing of the data, which can add bias to the result.¹² Additionally,

there is the matter of extensive computational costs, especially for substantial datasets. There is also the demand for a substantial amount of data to achieve peak performance, and it is a nontrivial task to find the optimal combination of hyperparameters. Moreover, deep learning methods are “black-boxes”, which makes their understanding and debugging a challenging task for a human analyst.¹⁶

Nevertheless, the benefits of the deep learning approach to imputation have led to the development of many models in a variety of areas. MIDASpy¹⁶ is an example of a Denoising Autoencoder. The authors have repurposed the Autoencoder by treating missing data as another part of the corrupted data. Then, imputations can be obtained from the model trained to minimize the reconstruction error.

The approach allows for the capture of complex relationships.

MIDAS can even achieve reasonably good performance under MNAR.¹⁶ However, it still suffers from the same issues as many other ML- and DL-based approaches. Additionally, MIDAS may underestimate the variance of posterior density, which can take place on the datasets containing many similar input–output pairs. However, the authors argue that the negative consequences of such conditions are debatable.

More approaches to the data imputation using autoencoders can be found for instance in Refs. 17–19.

While Autoencoders are well suited to handle incomplete data, there are many other approaches to missing data imputation using other deep learning-based methods. The authors of Ref. 20 propose a customized spatiotemporal deep learning architecture, called the graph convolutional bidirectional recurrent neural network (GCBRNN). Its goal is to impute online traffic data and perform predictions simultaneously. For this purpose, authors have also designed a network-scale graph convolutional gated recurrent unit. This unit can absorb the spatiotemporal patterns through the 1×1 convolution module and a graph convolution. The GCBRNN has outperformed selected competing methods in both the prediction and imputation during the tests.

Imputation of missing traffic data with deep learning was also tested in Ref. 21. The authors have used three methods, Stacked Autoencoders (SAEs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), as a part of their deep learning-based imputation and prediction (DLIP) model. SAEs²² are extensions of Autoencoders, where several Sparse Autoencoders are connected. The LSTM²³ and GRU²⁴ are a form of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) designed to solve the problems of vanishing and exploding gradient. The obtained results suggest that for the data with less than 40% of missing values imputations done by those models result in lower prediction errors when compared with more traditional methods.

Another example of a deep learning imputation method can be found in Ref. 25. There, a Deep Neural Network (DNN) was applied to replace missing values in attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) questionnaires. In the proposed framework, the DNN had been first trained to identify the best candidate questions to impute missing values. Afterwards, the question was added to the initial, complete training set to increase the number of features used to predict the next question.

This process was repeated iteratively for all the missing questions. The results show that the imputed datasets had a similar impact on the Support Vector Machine classifier as the referenced, complete data used in the experiment.

Two deep learning methods were proposed in Ref. 26 for gene expression imputation. The first of the two discussed solutions, Generative Adversarial Imputation Networks for GTE_x (GAIN-GTE_x) outclassed the comparable in-place imputation methods. The GAIN-GTE_x is based on Generative Adversarial Imputation Nets (GAIN),²⁷ which utilizes a competition between the generator and discriminator to estimate the generative model.

The second proposed method, Pseudo-Mask Imputer (PMI), has shown the highest performance in inductive imputation. It is a neural network where pseudo-mask mechanism is applied to hide parts of the observed components. Then, those hidden elements have to be recovered by the model at the output.

Finally, Ref. 28 presents a survey focused on the multivariable imputation task for time series. It describes the usage of Recurrent Neural Networks, Gated Recurrent units, Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN), and Bidirectional Recurrent Networks in this area. Those methods are either used separately or combined. Authors have listed five models found in the literature: GRU-D,²⁹ GRUI-GAN,³⁰ NAOMI,³¹ BRITS,³² and E²GAN.³³

GRU-D is a pure RNN approach using a Gated Recurrent Unit, while GRUI-GAN extends RNN with GAN to benefit from the imputation capabilities offered by Generative Adversarial models.

NAOMI (Non-AutoRegressive Multiresolution Imputation) is a hybrid model combining bidirectional RNN with GAN.²⁸ Moreover, NAOMI applies a “*divide and conquer predicting strategy*”.^{28,31}

Finally, BRITS is a bidirectional RNN model adopting “time lags” and “temporal decay factor”³² to better handle irregular time series.

Lastly, E²GAN expands the concept of GRUI-GAN by adopting the auto-encoder’s structure for the generator part of GAN, which is a common approach for image generation and imputation.²⁸ Authors of the survey²⁸ highlight its high, state-of-the-art performance.

As the examples above show, a variety of deep learning methods have found usage in the data imputation task. Especially approaches based on Autoencoders, Generative Adversarial Networks, or combinations of both are popular in this area, with the inclusion of recurrent models whenever time series are concerned. All of those methods offer powerful ability of capturing complex relationships in the data, at the cost of computational resources and potential problems characteristic for DL, such as overfitting, lack of transparency, etc.

3. What Missing Data are, and the Notion of Data Quality

In the broad sense, the quality of data can be characterized as *good* if, whenever used, the data are capable of producing a satisfactory result.³⁴ This might not be an

exact definition, but opens up the way to articulating data quality using metrics suitable for the use case. In Ref. 35, the data quality metrics of accuracy, coherence, uniqueness, compliance and completeness are discussed. The last criterion, completeness, pertains to the fact that the data are not null and provides sufficient information to formulate an efficient ML model. This goes along with the definition of missingness found in Ref. 7, where missing data are quite simply the values that are not present in the dataset. The author proposes a convenient way to think about missing values as a binary variable, which is either missing or not.^{7,35}

3.1. *Patterns of missingness*

Having established that a certain value is missing from the dataset, a question unfolds on the reason as to why the value is actually missing. This is referred to as the mechanism of missingness, or the pattern of missingness. The most commonly used classification of the patterns of missingness in contemporary research (Refs. 1, 7, 8, 36–49) follows the outline from Ref. 50, that is:

Missing Completely at Random (MCAR): In this situation, the null values are completely isolated and independent. To be more specific, this means that the values in question do not depend on other values that are missing, or on other values that are present in the dataset. MCAR data can inflate the standard errors, but do not contribute to systematic errors (bias — overestimation of benefits). MCAR, though incomplete, can be used to represent the entirety of the dataset. According to Ref. 38, this scenario is a rare case in the real world.

Missing At Random (MAR): In this less restrictive pattern, the values in question are not related to the missing data, but they are dependent on the data that is observed. In Ref. 8, this mechanism is illustrated by an example of a questionnaire inquiry of how many cigarettes per day the respondent smokes when the questionnaire is answered by a representative of a younger audience. Or the presence of the null response to a question about age being dependent on the sex variable.^{2,4} This mechanism opens up the way to inferring values of missing data from the complete cases.

Missing Not At Random (MNAR): When the values in question depend on the missing values themselves, the pattern is known as MNAR. By definition, the missing values are unknown, therefore recognising this pattern cannot be accomplished from the observed data. A respondent dropping out of a drug survey because of the effect the drug has on them is an example proposed by Ref. 3. This mechanism is sometimes referred to as informative missingness.⁴

The patterns of missingness represent completely different mechanisms of missing data. This form of understanding of the patterns of missingness bears serious ramifications.³ First of all, for MNAR data the fact of missingness itself holds information. Additionally, MNAR data cannot be inferred from the data in the dataset, hence there is no straightforward way to distinguish between MNAR and MAR patterns. The MAR data can be, up to a point, recovered from the rest of the

dataset.^{4,38} MAR data are not like MCAR, as it has a high chance to be the mechanism actually existing in real-life scenarios and research.³ Every pattern has its own potential solution.³ The potential for systematic error is influenced by both the mechanism of missingness and the volume of missing data. Since the specific pattern of missingness is hard to ascertain, so is the risk of bias. It is of utmost importance to take the steps to limit the damage missing data can have on the performance of the data-related inference systems.⁴ A formal description and understanding of the patterns of missingness enable the anticipation of potential consequences the null variables have³ on the performance of ML.

With regard to the amount of missing data Ref. 6 provides a brief guideline, where less than 1% of missing values are considered trivial, the 1–5% range is referred to as flexible. Missing between 5–15% of data calls for advanced methods. Anything above 15% bears immense impact on the results. In Ref. 4 the author recommends utmost care when dealing with large amounts of missing data, which is disclosed to be between 5–10% of the volume of the dataset.

The substantial volume, velocity, veracity and variety of data are the characteristics often described as the four V's of Big Data. The mentioned veracity hints at the noisy, incomplete, inaccurate or redundant samples of data. Variety suggests heterogeneity, which causes challenges in data integration and analytics. The multitude of sources and formats of data, along with the co-occurrence of the information pertaining to different aspects of a certain object in multiple modalities can allow to compensate for incomplete data coming from a single source.⁵¹

3.2. Dealing with missing values

A short primer of the general approach to researching the effects of handling of missing values can be found in Ref. 8. Four main steps are outlined.

- (a) The researcher is advised to collect more than one complete set of data on the investigated domain, with varied feature types and different lengths of the feature vector.
- (b) The null variables can be generated synthetically in a single (univariate) variable, or in more than one variable (multivariate), with a range of missing rates. The synthetic generation can follow the missingness mechanisms discussed earlier.
- (c) Dealing with the imputation approaches, either with statistical methods or with more intricate, ML-based algorithms. This step will be discussed at length.
- (d) Assessment of the results the chosen imputation methods had in the process of improving the results of the original task, in this case intrusion detection, using available performance metrics and comparing the results to the ground truth.⁸

4. Exploring Solutions

Complete Case Analysis (CCA). It only makes sense to start with one of the most popular approaches, as observed during the literature review. The reason for its

popularity might be due to the fact that it is suggested as the default option by many statistical software pieces.⁴

This approach, however, is one of the most problematic. Complete Case Analysis only uses the fully described datapoints as the basis for further analysis. This basically means that if a datapoint has a null record in any of its features, it is deleted. Hence, the method is also known under the name of Listwise Deletion.^{7,37} While it is the easy way out of the problem of missing values and is simple to implement, it comes with a significant price one has to be aware of. CCA forces any analysis performed on the newly formed dataset, including the ML algorithms, to effectively work with a reduced sample size, causing a higher propensity to worse performance metrics.⁴

It goes without saying that deleting the incomplete cases discards any information that might have been contained in those records. The loss of statistical power can, in some cases, be devastating to the analysis. The example showcased in Ref. 7 illustrates that in an unfortunate distribution of missing values across the dataset, the null records in 16% of cases can result in the deletion of 80% of the dataset. This does not seem like a viable option. The size of the dataset and the relevance of attributes need to be assessed before attempting deletion.⁴³

One more issue is whether the complete cases are a representative sample of the problem at hand. This could be true if the data are MCAR, but as mentioned earlier, in a real-world situation it is rarely the case.⁷

Another deletion form is *pairwise deletion*. This method is rooted in the variance-covariance matrix. As such, it is a more complete option than listwise deletion, as it relies on all the available data. However, as noted in Ref. 7, since the employed statistics use the records that exist, but omit the ones that are missing, variances and covariances are derived from different samples and thus the approximated parameters might be biased.^{7,52}

Single Imputation. Single imputation refers to a process where the missing variables are estimated using the observed values. By definition the single imputation approaches are geared towards handling data complying with the MAR mechanism.^{7,38} There is a range of possible choices in this category. The premise of the ‘last observation carried forward’ approach is that, as the name suggests, the last observation of a respondent is used to fill the missing value. This strategy is reserved to longitudinal studies. Similarly, the worst observation carried forward method pertains to using the worst observation of a subject.³⁸

Central Tendency Measures Substitution. Based on the reviewed literature, the three measures of central tendency — mean, median and mode — are used for imputation almost as frequently as listwise deletion.^{3,46} Mean substitution puts in the place of the null record the mean computed taking into account the distribution of all the existing inputs across one feature,^{7,37,43} which is considered a plausible value.² According to Ref. 7, this is the worst of all the possible strategies, and is on par with pretending that no data is missing. The reason for this assessment is the way this procedure disturbs the variance of the variable along with covariances and

correlations in the dataset.^{7,45} In Ref. 38, it is noted that using the single mean imputation dilutes the dataset as every missing value bears the same weight as the known one. Using the single mean imputation also presupposes that the unknown values are similar to the observed values. Using mean imputation on data not fulfilling that assumption might lead to bias. For missing categorical data, mode can be employed, while in a situation where the distribution is skewed, median is a better option.⁴³ The two main advantages of this imputation method are that it returns a complete dataset, allowing researchers to use all the available data, and it is very easy to implement.^{46,53}

Hot-Deck Imputation. The term hot-deck is a reference back to the times of punch cards, where the currently processed deck would literally be hot. The name suggests using data from the current dataset, as opposed to the ‘cold-deck’ imputation, where suitable candidates would be selected from external sources — data collected elsewhere, like a previous survey, or a different dataset. Hot-deck imputation methods rely on finding samples similar to the one with the null record and using the values copied from those samples.^{48,54} The donor samples are found through the auxiliary values via algorithms like the K-Nearest Neighbors.

Regression Imputation. Mean imputation disregards the remaining features of a datapoint, thus not taking its nature into account. Mean imputation treats all classes as if they were the same. To handle this shortcoming regression, imputation can be used.⁴ Regression imputation relies on considering the null value a dependent variable and using the remaining variables as features to form a regression model.³⁸ This definition presupposes there are relationships between the observed variables and the missing values,⁴⁸ making it an approach suitable for MAR data. The drawback of regression imputation is the loss of variability, which can, however, be restored by using stochastic regression imputation. This approach adds a stochastic value to the regression result, to make the imputed value more life-like.⁴⁸

Multiple Imputation. Multiple Imputation is an attempt to answer the drawbacks of single imputation. The approach relies on filling the missing values a number of times, which creates a number of datasets, and the results of this process are combined for processing.⁴⁶ The imputation step is done with a chosen imputation algorithm, drawing the results from a distribution of possible values. Multiple Imputation has been validated to handle null records in randomized clinical trials.³⁸ One drawback of using multiple imputation is its computational overhead.^{38,55}

Multiple Imputation: Matrix completion by iterative soft thresholding of Singular Value Decompositions (Soft Impute). Soft Impute iteratively replaces the null values in a dataset with values from a soft-thresholded Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). Using Soft Impute allows for smoothly calculating an entire regularization path of solutions on a grid of values of the regularization parameter, with only the SVD of a dense matrix being a computationally-heavy task, making it a scalable method of multiple imputation.⁵⁶

Multiple Imputation: MICE MICE, an acronym of Multiple Imputation with Chained Equations, is a multivariate technique for multiply imputing missing values using a sequence of regression models is a technique presented in Refs. 45, 57. The algorithm uses a sequence of regression models in order to model each missing value with regard to its distribution and achieve imputation.⁴⁵

Multiple Imputation: Matrix completion by iterative low-rank SVD decomposition (IterativeSVD/SVDimpute). The SVDimpute algorithm was developed by Ref. 58 in order to help facilitate gene expression microarray experiments, where fairly frequently the datasets come with multiple missing values. The authors, after multiple experiments, assess the robustness of their proposed methods as good as long as the amount of missing data does not exceed 20%. The method leverages singular value decomposition to acquire values equal to principal components of the gene expression matrix. The most significant of those values express most of the data. The procedure of IterativeSVD is redone up to the point where the total change is below a certain predetermined value.⁵⁸

K-Nearest Neighbor imputation. This approach utilizes the KNN algorithm, calculating a choice distance measure (euclidean, jaccard, minkowski, etc.) on variables observed in both donor and recipient samples.^{37,43,46,53} The algorithm uses k most similar donor samples with non-null records to the recipient sample of the variable in question. The imputed value is either the most common value in the neighbors, or an average of those values.⁴⁹ The main drawback of this approach is poor scalability.⁴⁵ KNN Imputation is a very resource-heavy process and thus it is not usable in situations where the dataset is sizable. For this reason, the KNN imputation method is omitted from this study.

MissForest. MissForest is an adaptation of the Random Forest algorithm to an imputation method capable of dealing with mixed-type data. The Random Forest algorithm is known for good performance in difficult conditions, like high dimensions, complex interactions and nonlinear data structures. The authors of Ref. 59 perform a series of experiments and conclude that missForest outperforms both KNN-Imputation and MICE.⁵⁹

Deep Learning Imputation. The rising popularity of Deep Learning has lead to the development of imputation methods utilizing this paradigm. Those have found applications in numerous contexts, from agriculture, through online network traffic to genetics. The following subsection serves as a reference point for some of the recent developments in this area.

5. Experimental Setup and Results

This section presents the methodology and results of the two experimental campaigns. It starts with an outline summarizing the core ideas of the experiments. Then, in Sec. 5.2, both datasets are described in detail, including applied

transformations, changes, and rules to simulate the MAR mechanism. In Secs. 5.3 and 5.4, obtained results are communicated. Finally, the last subsection discusses the outcomes of both campaigns.

5.1. *Experimental outline*

Two separate sets of experiments were conducted for this work.

During the first one, six different approaches to missing values are evaluated, and their influence on the results of the Random Forest algorithm trained using the CICIDS2017 intrusion detection benchmark dataset is assessed.

The purpose of the second experiment was to compare some common imputation methods with state-of-the-art deep learning imputation for highly incomplete data. The test was conducted using a Balanced Random Forest Algorithm trained on a subset of IoT-23 dataset,¹¹ a well-known intrusion detection benchmark.

5.2. *Dataset preparation*

To conduct the experiments, the CICIDS2017⁶⁰ dataset and the IoT-23¹¹ dataset were used.

Intrusion Detection Evaluation Dataset — CICIDS2017 is the effect of the endeavor to construct a reliable and current dataset in the domain of network intrusion detection. Datasets in the cybersecurity domain are particularly cumbersome to acquire. The ones that are accessible display some of the discouraging perturbations, like insufficiency of traffic diversity, attack variety, superfluous features and so on. The authors of CICIDS2017 attempt to answer this need for realistic cyber datasets. CICIDS is an annotated capture of benign and malicious traffic. The attack captures contain malware, DoS attacks, web attacks and others. CICIDS2017 is currently one of the rare state-of-the-art datasets available to researchers.

The dataset has an unbalanced distribution of classes, with the BENIGN class being the majority class. The lack of class balance can become a problem for ML classifiers.⁶¹ To counter this problem and prevent the impact an imbalanced dataset can have on the classifier, the majority class was randomly subsampled.

To prepare the dataset for imputation, a number of values were removed based on conditions pertaining to different values (for example, in the feature ‘*Destination Port*’ values were deleted if the value of ‘*Bwd Packet Length Max*’ exceeded 443, which constitutes about 25% of the ‘*Destination Port*’ variables). This is to imitate MAR missingness mechanism. Collectively, about 15% of the values in the testing part of the dataset were deleted.

The labeled dataset with malicious and benign Internet-of-Things (IoT) network traffic — IoT-23 — is a more recent cybersecurity dataset from January 2020. It contains network traffic gathered from IoT devices during the 2018 to 2019 period. It has 20 scenarios with malware capture and three with benign traffic, where all samples come obtained from real hardware in a controlled network environment. The full dataset features 16 different classes and 23 columns with a total of 325,307,990 captures.

For the experiment, a subset of the IoT 23 consisting of the following scenarios was used:

- CTU-IoT-Malware-Capture-7-1 (Linux.Mirai),
- CTU-IoT-Malware-Capture-1-1 (Hide and Seek),
- CTU-IoT-Malware-Capture-60-1 (Gagfyt),
- CTU-IoT-Malware-Capture-34-1 (Mirai),
- CTU-IoT-Malware-Capture-36-1 (Okiru) (only samples for C&C-HeartBeat).

As the result, the data used for the experiment had 16,083,327 distinct captures available, representing five types of traffic (one class was removed due to very low sample count):

- **Benign**,
- **DDoS attack**,
- **Okiru attack**,
- **Part of a Horizontal Port Scan attack**,
- **C&C-HeartBeat attack**.

After careful selection, eight features out of the original 23 were used. Those were:

- **conn_state** — categorical feature representing state of the connection,
- **history** — categorical feature representing history of the connection state,
- **orig_pkts** — number of packets being sent to the device,
- **orig_ip_bytes** — number of bytes being sent to the device,
- **resp_pkts** — number of packets being sent from the device,
- **resp_ip_bytes** — number of bytes being sent from the device
- **proto** — categorical feature representing type of the employed protocol (one-hot-encoded),
- **label** — target categorical feature which was created by integrating “*detailed-label*” column with original “*label*”.

Rare positions in columns “*conn_state*” and “*history*” were grouped together and assigned to the new value “*other*” to reduce cardinality. Then, the Leave-One-Out Encoders were used on both columns to transform them to numerical form. It was done separately for the train and test data portions to avoid data leakage.

The column “*proto*” was transformed with a one-hot-encoder, while the label encoder was used for “*label*” column.

Data were split with 75% of all values forming train set and the rest used for a test portion. Additionally, to simulate the MAR mechanism, missing values were introduced to the test data using the following set of rules:

- (a) **IF** encoded “*history*” value in the row is **LESS THAN 2**, remove value in the column “*orig_ip_bytes*”,
- (b) **IF** “*orig_pkts*” value in the row is **EQUAL TO OR GREATER THAN 2**, remove value in the column “*orig_ip_bytes*”,

- (c) **IF** “proto” value in the row **IS** UDP, remove value in the column “orig_ip_bytes”,
- (d) **IF** “proto” value in the row **IS** UDP, remove value in the column “resp_pkts”,
- (e) **IF** encoded “history” value in the row is **LESS THAN 2**, remove value in the column “resp_pkts”,
- (f) **IF** “orig_pkts” value in the row is **EQUAL TO OR GREATER THAN 2**, remove value in the column “resp_ip_bytes”,
- (g) **IF** encoded “history” value in the row is **GREATER THAN 2**, remove value in the column “orig_pkts”.

Those rules resulted in the 10%, 7%, 3%, and 41% of data missing in columns “orig_ip_bytes”, “resp_pkts”, “resp_ip_bytes”, and “orig_pkts” accordingly, making it an extremely difficult scenario.

It should be mentioned that while there were some incomplete samples at the beginning, they were removed to avoid unexpected impact on the experiment. Moreover, based on the data analysis and experimentation, data points belonging to the category of “Okiru attack” were randomly undersampled, reducing 11,326,712 samples to 2,265,342. It was done in order to achieve a more balanced distribution of classes in the dataset, in accordance with Refs. 62 and 63 and had no negative impact on the model’s predictions.

5.3. Results of the first experimental campaign

The effect of the imputation methods on the variable distribution of two of the affected features is illustrated by the density plots in Figs. 1 and 2. Even a very brief inspection of the distributions makes it clear to what extent the mean imputation distorts the nature of the dataset. The remaining imputation methods at least to some extent follow the distribution pattern of the original, full dataset. A clear winner comes in the performance of MissForest, which was able to retrieve the original distribution of values with surprising accuracy. This fact is also reflected in the results of the classifier.

Fig. 1. The density plot of the Packet Length Std feature with different imputation methods influencing the distribution of feature values in different ways (CICIDS2017).

Fig. 2. The density plot of the ‘Bwd Packet length Std’ feature with different imputation methods influencing the distribution of feature values in different ways (CICIDS2017).

The features considered in the experiment were selected using the `feature_importances_` property from `sklearn.ensemble.ExtraTreesClassifier`. Top 10 most important features in CICIDS2017 were picked. These are ‘PSH Flag Count’, ‘Destination Port’, ‘Packet Length Std’, ‘min_seg_size_forward’, ‘Bwd Packet Length Std’, ‘Avg Bwd Segment Size’, ‘Bwd Packet Length Mean’, ‘Bwd Packet Length Min’, ‘Average Packet Size’, and ‘Bwd Packet Length Max’. The class labels were accessible to the imputation algorithms, only to the classifier at test time.

In the experiment, the chosen classifier — `RandomForest` — was trained using the complete cases in the training part of the dataset. The training set was randomly sampled from the whole dataset; 60% of the dataset was used.

The iterative_SVD, MICE, SoftImpute, MissForest Mean Imputation and List-wise Deletion approaches were tested. The influence the selected approaches had over the IDS classifier can be found in Tables 1–3. The imputation methods were implemented using `missingpy`, `fancyimpute`⁶⁴ and `sklearn.impute`⁶⁵ packages.

The impact of imputation is measured by the classical metrics: accuracy, precision, recall and f-1 score. The imputation methods are the only variable in the experiment — the classifier and the data used are exactly the same, with the

Table 1. Accuracy obtained by Random Forest tested on datasets obtained using different imputation methods (CICIDS2017).

Method	Accuracy
SoftImpute	0.9207
Mean Imputation	0.8357
MissForest	0.9565
MICE	0.9302
iterative_SVD	0.8405
Before_missing	0.9856

Table 2. Random Forest over data augmented with MissForest Imputation (CICIDS2017).

	Precision	Recall	f1-score
BENIGN	0.98	0.99	0.98
Bot	0.71	0.46	0.56
DDoS	1.00	0.82	0.90
DoS GoldenEye	1.00	0.49	0.65
DoS Hulk	0.88	0.98	0.93
DoS Slowhttptest	0.75	0.92	0.82
DoS slowloris	0.99	0.68	0.81
FTP-Patator	1.00	1.00	1.00
Heartbleed	0.00	0.00	0.00
Infiltration	1.00	0.07	0.13
PortScan	1.00	1.00	1.00
SSH-Patator	0.83	0.49	0.62
Web Attack Brute Force	1.00	0.04	0.07
Web Attack Sql Injection	0.00	0.00	0.00
Web Attack XSS	0.00	0.00	0.00
Accuracy			0.96
Macro avg	0.74	0.53	0.57
Weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.95

Table 3. Random Forest over data obtained by complete case analysis (CICIDS2017).

	Precision	Recall	f1-score
BENIGN	1.00	1.00	1.00
DDoS	1.00	1.00	1.00
DoS Hulk	0.98	0.99	0.98
DoS slowloris	0.00	0.00	0.00
PortScan	1.00	1.00	1.00
Accuracy			1.00
Macro avg	0.79	0.80	0.80
Weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00

exception of listwise deletion, which, by its very nature, deletes the incomplete cases and thus makes the obtained results hard to compare. These can be investigated in Table 3. It is critical to note that listwise deletion eliminated 10 out of 14 classes of the attacks available in the CICIDS2017 dataset. The accuracy obtained by the classifier on the testing dataset before missing values were created is given in Table 1, along with the accuracy of other methods.

5.4. Results of the second experimental campaign

The second experimental campaign was conducted on a subset of IoT-23 datasets prepared as described in Sec. 5.2. During the tests, Mean Imputation, MissForest Imputation, Iterative Imputer using Bayesian Ridge (a variant of MICE⁶⁵) and Deep Learning Imputation were used and compared.

Table 4. Accuracy obtained by Balanced Random Forest Classifier tested on datasets obtained using different imputation methods (IoT-23).

Method	Accuracy
Mean Imputation	0.9119
MissForest	0.9117
Iterative Imputation	0.6362
Deep Learning Imputation	0.9549
No missing data	0.9630

Balanced Random Forest Classifier had the number of estimators set to 200. Deep Learning Imputation network was composed of three layers with 256 units each. Parameter probability of corruption for input in the training mini-batches was set to 0.85, while the number of used training epochs was 20. Iterative Imputer was limited to a maximum of 10 iterations.

The main goal of the experiment was to compare the impact of the deep learning approach to missing data handling on the classifier with other effective approaches in the context of heavily depleted cybersecurity data.

The comparison of model accuracy after each imputation method with the scenario when there was no incomplete data is represented in Table 4. Considering accuracy alone, the Deep Learning Imputation significantly outclassed other approaches in the presented scenario.

When confusion matrices from Fig. 3 are compared, the effect of imputation techniques and their impact on the final results becomes transparent. The model where mean imputation was used seemed to achieve a percentage of correctly classified samples similar to the baseline model. However, it realistically reduced the effectiveness introducing a substantial amount of false negatives and decreasing precision for Benign traffic by 37 percentage points (p.p).

A comparable situation occurred for the experiment in which Iterative Imputation with Bayesian Ridge was used. Even though its confusion matrix resembles the base case, it misclassified all traffic belonging to the Okiru attack as Benign. Since this is the most numerous class, it drastically affected both accuracy and precision for the Benign samples, decreasing it to 17%.

MissForest imputation was the first method in the comparison that did not introduce numerous false negatives. Misclassifications occurred within various malign traffic examples and predominantly problematic for the baseline model. The main issue in this case is the inability to detect portscan attacks, treating them as C&C or Okiru attacks.

The analysis of the Deep Learning Imputation approach experiment shows that the model could achieve a classification level close to the baseline for Benign, DDoS, Okiru, and PortScan traffic, struggling only with C&C. It could be caused by the comparably low number of data samples for this attack, with 5443 data points. An increased number of samples could lead to a better performance.

Fig. 3. Comparison of confusion matrices resulting from used imputation methods (IoT-23).

Table 5 collects and compares detailed results of the model without incomplete data and the ones using either MissForest or Deep Learning Imputation. It further clarifies where those imputation methods had an advantage. The model with MissForest was minimally better in the case of the Benign class and achieved much

Table 5. Comparison of classification results between model without missing data with models where data was imputed using MissForest and Deel Learning (IoT-23).

Class	Imputation	Precision	Recall	f1-score
BENIGN	No Missing	0.95	0.92	0.93
	MissForest	0.92	0.92	0.92
	Deep Learning Imputation	0.89	0.92	0.90
C&C-HeartBeat	No Missing	0.06	0.59	0.11
	MissForest	0.03	0.56	0.06
	Deep Learning Imputation	0.15	0.15	0.15
DDoS	No Missing	1.00	0.99	1.00
	MissForest	1.00	0.99	0.99
	Deep Learning Imputation	1.00	0.99	0.99
Okiru	No Missing	1.00	1.00	1.00
	MissForest	0.92	1.00	0.96
	Deep Learning Imputation	0.92	1.00	0.96
PartOfAHorizontalPortScan	No Missing	0.90	0.66	0.76
	MissForest	0.98	0.02	0.03
	Deep Learning Imputation	0.90	0.62	0.73
	Accuracy			0.96
No Missing	Macro avg	0.78	0.83	0.76
	Weighted avg	0.99	0.96	0.97
	Accuracy			0.91
MissForest	Macro avg	0.77	0.70	0.59
	Weighted avg	0.96	0.91	0.90
	Accuracy			0.95
Deep Learning Imputation	Macro avg	0.77	0.73	0.75
	Weighted avg	0.95	0.95	0.95

higher recall for C&C-HeartBeat. However, the model using Deep Learning Imputation outclassed it in traffic belonging to the PartOfAHorizontalPortScan, thus achieving a better overall score.

5.5. Summary of results

As evident by inspecting the accuracy of the RF classifier over the dataset obtained by different imputation methods, the choice of the method has serious impact over the results achieved by the classifier.

During the first experimental campaigns, the **MissForest** imputation method provided the data that allowed the classifier to reach the highest accuracy — 96% (Table 2). The next best result came with the data obtained by using MICE — 93%, closely followed by 92% obtained by SoftImpute. Of the two most often employed missing data handling strategies, one gave sub-par results (mean imputation), the other completely decimated the dataset (Listwise deletion/Complete case analysis — Table 3).

In the second experimental campaign simulating the data with the high level of incompleteness, the deep learning-based approach outperformed the competition.

The model which used output provided by this method achieved the best accuracy equal to 95% (Tables 4 and 5). The resulting score was only one percentage point lower than in the case of the model without missing data. Furthermore, it was higher by almost four percentage points than the accuracy of the model using MissForest. However, closer inspection of Table 5 and Fig. 3 reveals that MissForest also provided its model with high-quality imputed data, thus outclassing the remaining approaches. The resulting model was even minimally more precise when classifying Benign traffic than the model paired with Deep Learning Imputation.

6. Conclusion

In this work, the problem of handling missing values in intrusion detection has been addressed. The work opens with an introduction to the problem of data quality and missing data, the missingness mechanisms are introduced and discussed. The work continues with an inventory of approaches to dealing with missing data, along with the most applicable algorithms in the context of network intrusion detection. The pros and cons of the methods were disclosed. Then, the details of the experimental campaigns are given and the obtained results are communicated. As presented in Tables 1, 4 and Fig. 3, the choice of the imputation method can have a critical impact on the results of the classification method employed in intrusion detection. Especially in IDS, deleting samples just because they contain some missing values can have serious consequences. The conducted experiments answer RQ1 and confirm RQ2. On top of that, simply substituting the missing values with a central tendency measure not only distorts the nature of the data, but produces sub-par results when compared to more robust methods. The difference between the worst and the best obtained accuracies exceeds 12 percentage points. Using complete case analysis in the evaluated case eliminated exactly 10 attack classes with only 15% missing values in the dataset.

Furthermore, as the second experiment has shown, imputation methods based on deep learning can perform well with heavily depleted data.

While deep learning-based methods can outclass other algorithms in the data imputation task, especially when a high level of missingness is considered, machine learning algorithms such as MissForest are an attractive alternative.

Thus, the answer to RQ3 is Deep Learning Imputation and missForrest are best suited for handling missing data in cybersecurity applications.

In the future, this work could be expanded with comparison focused solely on Deep Learning Imputation methods and their impact on selected machine learning-based classifiers. At the same time, explainability methods could be employed⁶⁶ to research the complex relationships in data that Deep Learning Imputation highlights for the successful completion of its task. Finally, using the latent representation of autoencoders could be expanded upon different granularity levels⁶⁷ for pushing the effectiveness of imputation even further.

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